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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	7
1.2 Structure of the Document	7
2. Extended Services for Lab Automation	8
2.1 Configuration Management	8
2.2 Workflow	8
2.3 Proof of Concept	9
3. Automation Testing Setup	12
3.1 Motivation and Use Cases	12
3.2 Automation Testing Process	13
3.3 Automation Testing Workflow	13
3.4 An Example of Automation Testing Experiment	15
4. Virtual Access	19
4.1 Simulation-as-a-Service Prototype	19
5. Conclusions	23
References	24

List of Figures

Figure 1: Configuration management schematic.....	8
Figure 2: CM tool workflow (i.e., <i>Yaml</i> files are shown in orange and Python scripts in blue).	9
Figure 3: The relationship between JRA3 and JRA2 in ERIGrid 2.0.....	12
Figure 4: Overview of the automation testing workflow.....	14
Figure 5: Overview of the test sequences loop.....	15
Figure 6: Overview of an automation testing setup with PHIL in CEA.....	16
Figure 7: Overview of the communication setup.	16
Figure 8: Architecture of the Simulation-as-a-Service (SaaS) prototype.....	20
Figure 9: Architecture of the Dynamic Phasor Simulator, DPSim.....	21
Figure 10: Screenshot of one of the Jupyter notebooks of the SaaS prototype.....	22

List of Abbreviations

ACS	Automation of Complex Power Systems
API	Application Programming Interface
CM	Configuration Management
CIM	Common Information Model
DaaS	Data-as-a-Service
EUT	Equipment Under Test
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
JRA	Joint Research Activity
LVRT	Low Voltage Ride Through
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
RI	Research Infrastructure
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
SaaS	Simulation-as-a-Service
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SUT	System Under Test
SVG	Scalable Vector Graphics
uAPI	Universal Application Programming Interface
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report summaries the work undertaken in ERIGrid 2.0 towards improved and extended Research Infrastructure (RI) services (i.e., integration, coupling, and automation). More specifically, the following work is covered:

1. Development of a Configuration Management (CM) tool to greatly improve the automation and reproducibility of multi-RI experiments. This tool plays a pivotal role in managing and maintaining experiment configurations, ensuring consistency and reliability in the experimental research process.
2. Creation of automation sequences and scripts designed to automate the configuration and execution of simulation-based experiments. These scripts streamline the process of setting up and running simulations, thereby improving the efficiency and accuracy of workflows.
3. Deployment of Simulation-as-a-Service (SaaS) for virtual laboratory access. This facilitates convenient and scalable virtual access to laboratory infrastructures, thereby enhancing accessibility.

Together, these implementations underscore the advancement in the capabilities of RIs by incorporating automation, reproducibility, and enhanced access through innovative virtual services.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document provides a summary of the work undertaken in the second half of *Work Package (WP)12-Joint Research Activity (JRA)3 – Improved and Extended Services (RI integration, coupling, and automation)* focused on improved and extended Services for RI integration, coupling, and automation. In particular, three different implementations are addressed:

- CM service for improved multi-RI experiment automation and reproducibility,
- Scripts for automation of simulation configurations and runs, and
- SaaS for virtual lab access.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The remainder of this document is organised as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the software development of the configuration management service, while Section 3 covers the tool development for automation of simulation configurations and runs. The developed Simulation-as-a-Service prototype for virtual lab access is described in Section 4. Finally, a key summary of the main outcomes is provided in Section 5.

2 Extended Services for Lab Automation

2.1 Configuration Management

To establish a comprehensive CM strategy that facilitates automated data exchange configuration for multi-RI experiments, a CM tool was developed. Currently, the configuration process for laboratory coupling tools used in multi-RI experiments from project partners, such as VILLAS, JaNDER, or Lablink is intricate, manual, and error-prone (*D-JRA3.1 Distributed Laboratory Middleware, 2023*).

To address these challenges, a dedicated CM tool to automate the task of configuring data exchange for experiments spanning multiple RIs was developed. The core concept involves the creation of an offline global configuration file or blueprint that outlines the seamless flow of data across the collaborating RIs. Additionally, an online mechanism is implemented to automatically map local signals of individual RIs to corresponding data channels based on the overarching global description.

Adopting this innovative approach significantly simplifies the CM process. This leads to simplified and reproducible multi-RI experiments, eliminating the complexities associated with manual configurations. The outcome is a refined and efficient method that ensures smoother data exchange configuration, fosters easier experiment replication, and ultimately enhances the quality of multi-RI experiments. The above-described concept is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Configuration management schematic.

2.2 Workflow

The workflow of the developed CM tool is shown in Figure 2 and summarised as follows:

1. The first step is the creation of an offline global configuration file which contains all the relevant information about the multi-RI experiment. This includes the participating RIs, signals to be exchanged, type of tool to be used, etc. The file is developed to be machine-readable and is currently based on “.yaml” file format. An example of this file is shown in

code Listing 1.

2. The next step in the process is the parser tool, developed in Python. It takes the global configuration file as an input and generates the associated object-oriented node instances for each participating RI.
3. The outputs from the parser are then used by the processor to identify the local configurations for each participating RI. It takes the node instances and generates the instances of the desired local configuration objects.
4. As the last step, the serializer generates the desired local configuration *yaml* files, based on the outputs of the processor. These files can then be used to partially automate the configurations/experimental settings in the participating RIs.

All the aforementioned tools, i.e., the parser, processor, and serializer are developed as Python v3.9 scripts.

Figure 2: CM tool workflow (i.e., *Yaml* files are shown in orange and Python scripts in blue).

2.3 Proof of Concept

The Proof-of-Concept (PoC) phase is a critical step in developing any new technology or tool. It serves as a preliminary testing ground to validate key ideas and functionalities before committing to full-scale development (Oleksandr Yatsuta, 2023).

The primary objectives of the PoC for the proposed CM tool are to finalise the *Yaml* template for global and local configurations, define the components and architecture of the CM tool, create a simple Minimum Viable Product (MVP) use case for initial testing, and develop an object-oriented skeleton in Python.

To achieve the defined objectives, the following tasks were successfully completed:

- Creation of the “Yaml” template for global and local configurations for the multi-RI experiments. An example of this file is shown in code Listing 1,

- Definition of the CM tool's components and architecture,
- Development of an object-oriented skeleton in Python for the proposed CM tool, and
- Development and testing of a simple MVP use case for initial testing whereas the generated local configuration files for RI 1 and 2 from the global configuration according to the code Listing 1 are shown in code Listing 2 and Listing 3.

Listing 1: Global configuration file for a two-RI experiment.

```

1  # MVP config
2  nodes:
3    ri1:
4      description: "Research infrastructure 1"
5
6      uapi_endpoint: "http://localhost:8081" # Optional
7
8      channels: # This node provides (sources) these channels
9
10     - { id: "ri1::rtids:f", unit: Hz, rate: 10.0, description: "PCC frequency" }
11     - { id: "ri1::rtids:U", unit: kV, rate: 10.0, description: "PCC voltage"}
12
13     transport:
14       type: villas
15
16       # All following attributes are specific to the type of transport
17       # and not covered by the global config schema.
18       villas-node:
19         api-host: localhost
20         api-port: 9001
21         node-type: udp
22
23     ri2:
24       description: "Research infrastructure 2"
25
26       uapi_endpoint: "http://localhost:8082" # Optional
27
28       channels: # This node provides (sources) these channels
29
30       - { id: "ri2::amp:P", unit: mW, rate: 10.0, description: "Amplifier active power measurement"}
31       - { id: "ri2::amp:Q", unit: pu, rate: 10.0, description: "Amplifier reactive power measurement"}
32
33       transport:
34         type: villas
35
36         # All following attributes are specific to the type of transport
37         # and not covered by the global config schema.
38         villas-node:
39           api-host: localhost
40           api-port: 9002
41           node-type: udp
42
43     connections:
44     - {from: "ri1::rtids:f", to-ri: "ri2", to-channel: "ri2::amp:f"}
45     - {from: "ri1::rtids:U", to-ri: "ri2", to-channel: "ri2::amp:U"}
46     - {from: "ri2::amp:P", to-ri: "ri1", to-channel: "ri1::rtids:P"}
47     - {from: "ri2::amp:Q", to-ri: "ri1", to-channel: "ri1::rtids:Q"}
48     - {resolvers: {nodes: [ri1, ri2], resolver: peer-to-peer}}
49
50
51     ri_adapters: #probably to be moved to local lab configurations
52     - type: mvp_adapter
53
54     nodes:
55     - ri1
56     - ri2

```

Listing 2: Local configuration file for RI 1.

```

1 # Local RI 1 mvp config
2 nodes:
3   uapi_endpoint: http://localhost:8081
4
5   channels: # This node provides (sources) these channels
6     incoming:
7       - { id: ri2::amp:P}
8       - { id: ri2::amp:Q}
9     outgoing:
10      - { id: ri1::rtids:f, unit: Hz, rate: 10.0, description: "PCC frequency" }
11      - { id: ri1::rtids:U, unit: kV, rate: 10.0, description: "PCC voltage" }
12
13   transport:
14     type: villas
15
16     # All following attributes are specific to the type of transport
17     # and not covered by the global config schema.
18     villas-node:
19       api-host: localhost
20       api-port: 9001
21       node-type: udp
22
23     resolver-result:
24       startup: yes
25       address-outgoing: "localhost:4445"
26       address-incoming: "localhost:4446"
27
28   ri_adapters: #probably to be moved to local lab configurations
29     - type: mvp_adapter
30
31     nodes:
32     - ri1
33     - ri2

```

Listing 3: Local configuration file for for RI 2.

```

1 # Local RI 2 mvp config
2 nodes:
3   uapi_endpoint: http://localhost:8082
4
5   channels: # This node provides (sources) these channels
6     incoming:
7       - { id: ri1::rtids:f}
8       - { id: ri2::rtids:U}
9     outgoing:
10      - { id: ri2::amp:P, unit: mW, rate: 10.0, description: "Amplifier active power measurement" }
11      - { id: ri1::amp:Q, unit: pu, rate: 10.0, description: "Amplifier reactive power measurement" }
12
13   transport:
14     type: villas
15
16     # All following attributes are specific to the type of transport
17     # and not covered by the global config schema.
18     villas-node:
19       api-host: localhost
20       api-port: 9002
21       node-type: udp
22
23     resolver-result:
24       startup: yes
25       address-outgoing: "localhost:4446"
26       address-incoming: "localhost:4445"
27
28   ri_adapters: #probably to be moved to local lab configurations
29     - type: mvp_adapter
30
31     nodes:
32     - ri1
33     - ri2

```

3 Automation Testing Setup

3.1 Motivation and Use Cases

In ERIGrid 2.0, the tasks undertaken in this section are closely linked to task JRA3.4, which aims to enable all the project-related RIs with a machine-to-machine interface to be operated in an as automated fashion as possible. Moreover, the CM strategy developed in JRA2.3 for automation configuration mentioned in Section 2 served as an input for this work. This relationship is presented in Figure 3. Therefore, a method for automation testing with a parameter sweeps approach will be developed in this section.

Figure 3: The relationship between JRA3 and JRA2 in ERIGrid 2.0.

In terms of concept, automating tests involves translating a manual test case into a machine-readable format. This representation may take the form of a program in a commonly used programming or scripting language (such as Java or Python). Alternatively, automation can occur by structuring a test case as a series of keywords or calls to executable subroutines, accompanied by the necessary arguments. This sequence can be automatically interpreted by a driver program, enabling automated execution of the test case (Thummalapenta, Sinha, Singhanian, & Chandra, 2012). These specialised programs/scripts facilitate the execution of various tests by specifying data to the System Under Test (SUT).

The utilisation of automation testing brings the following advantages:

- The manual testing of various workflows, fields, and scenarios is a time-consuming process,
- Test automation in software testing operates without human intervention, allowing for unattended automated tests to be run, even overnight,
- Automation significantly accelerates the speed of test execution, and
- Automated testing aids in expanding test coverage, ensuring a more comprehensive assessment of the software.

The motivation to employ automation testing under specific circumstances is due to the following reasons:

- Test cases that are repeatedly executed; any automation is effective only for the repetitive processes,
- Test cases that involve tasks overly laborious or challenging to conduct manually; as the workload intensifies, individuals are prone to making an increasing number of errors, and
- Test cases that consume a significant amount of time during manual execution.

3.2 Automation Testing Process

In this subsection, several steps of an automated test are proposed. By following this procedure, a continuous improvement loop is maintained, allowing for enhancements and optimisations in the automated testing process. There are five steps:

1. *Test tool selection:* This initial phase entails carefully selecting the appropriate testing Equipment Under Test (EUT) and SUT that align with the project's requirements and objectives. This involves evaluating various automated testing software and hardware that are available in the RIs to choose the most appropriate ones.
2. *Definition automation scope:* This step involves identifying and determining which aspects of testing can benefit most from automation. This step involves analysing test cases, processes, and functionalities that can be effectively automated to enhance efficiency and accuracy in testing.
3. *Design and development:* Once the scope is established, the planning, design, and development phase initiates. This stage involves devising comprehensive strategies and creating automation scripts or programs to execute identified test cases and scenarios.
4. *Test execution and result analysis:* After the creation of automation scripts, the actual testing phase begins. Automated tests are executed using the selected tools to validate software or systems against predefined criteria. This step involves running the scripts, analysing results, and identifying any discrepancies or issues.
5. *Maintenance:* The last step involves the regular upkeep of the automated testing suite. This includes updating scripts, modifying test cases as per changes in software requirements, debugging scripts, and ensuring the automated testing process remains efficient and effective over time.

3.3 Automation Testing Workflow

In this part, the automation testing workflow as shown in Figure 4 is proposed and outlined as a structured approach to conduct comprehensive testing in a controlled environment.

Each step contributes to creating a robust testing framework that ensures reliability and accuracy in assessing the performance of the tested system. The following are the steps:

1. *Define Tested Scenario:* This initial step involves outlining the specific scenarios or use cases that will be tested. It is crucial to identify the functionalities or behaviours of the system that need validation.

Figure 4: Overview of the automation testing workflow.

2. *Define Tested Model*: In this stage, a detailed description or model of the system under test is established. This model helps in understanding the expected behaviour, inputs, outputs, and dependencies of the system, forming the basis for testing.
3. *Define Controlled Parameters*: In this phase, the parameters that will be controlled or manipulated during the testing process are identified. These parameters could include variables such as input values, environmental conditions, or system settings.
4. *Get Controlled Parameters Signal Names*: This step involves precisely identifying and documenting the signal names or identifiers associated with the controlled parameters. This documentation ensures accuracy in setting up the test environment and executing the tests.
5. *Test Sequences Loop*: This is the core phase where the actual testing takes place. Test sequences, comprising a series of actions, are designed and executed systematically. The controlled parameters are adjusted within these sequences to observe and analyse how the system responds under varying conditions. The details about this step are presented in Figure 5.
6. *Data Analysis*: Following the test sequences execution, the collected data is analysed. This step involves examining the system's behaviour, performance metrics, error handling, and any anomalies observed during testing. The aim is to derive insights into the system's performance and identify areas that may require improvement or further testing.

Figure 5: Overview of the test sequences loop.

3.4 An Example of Automation Testing Experiment

3.4.1 Test Setup

In this part, an example of automation testing with a parameter sweeps approach is demonstrated. The overall Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) setup is presented in Figure 6 and the detail for communication setup is shown in Figure 7. These are the main features of this test:

- *Scenario:* Automation testing the Low Voltage Ride Through (LVRT) function of a real three-phase inverter. The inverter is connected to a virtual microgrid in which the load profiles will be modified by an automation script.
- *EUT and SUT:* DC source, SMA inverter, OPAL-RT OP5700, power amplifier, RT-LAB application, MATLAB/Simulink 2016b, and Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA).
- *Scope of Automation:* The inverter LVRT function performance with different grid configurations (i.e., load profile variation). The power set points of the inverter can be controlled through the SCADA system during the test.
- *Design:* A low-voltage microgrid is developed in the MATLAB/Simulink environment. The automation script is developed in Python Application Programming Interface (API). The PV profiles are emulated with a DC source. The power amplifier acts as an interface between the real-time simulator (i.e., OPAL-RT OP5700) and the SMA inverter.
- *Test execution:* 10 different parameters (i.e., load profiles) for 10 automated tests with at least 300 seconds of running time per test.
- *Results analysis:* Powers and LVRT curve profiles.

Figure 6: Overview of an automation testing setup with PHIL in CEA.

Figure 7: Overview of the communication setup.

3.4.2 Automation Script for Parameter Sweeps

The example code in Listing 4 presents how to create a script in Python API to run a test sequence with PHIL. It demonstrates how to change variables during runtime, run a Python API script with RT-LAB, and run test sequences using a Python script. The results are located in MATLAB. The Python script will perform the following steps:

- Open MATLAB/Simulink and connect to the microgrid model,
- Compile the model,
- Load the model,
- Connect the SMA inverter,
- Change load profiles value,
- Run the test for 150 seconds,
- Reset the model,
- Save results in mat files, and
- Close.

Listing 4: Python example script.

```
1 import RtlabApi
2 import time
3 import random
4
5 # Define variables
6 projectName='D:\Pham\Pham_Automation_Test\Pham_Automation_Test.llp'
7 paramPL='Tuan_Test_PV3P_V2/SM_main/Simulated_network/Controlled_P_Gain/Gain'
8 signalName='Tuan_Test_PV3P_V2/sc_mesure/port1(16)'
9 paramName=(paramPL)
10
11 # Acquire controlled parameters
12 def Test_Sequence(paramPL, test_num):
13     print 'Test Sequence #' + str(test_num)
14     realTimeMode = RtlabApi.HARD_SYNC_MODE
15     RtlabApi.Load(realTimeMode,1)
16     print('Model has been loaded')
17
18     RtlabApi.Execute(1)
19     print('Model is running')
20
21     #Get control
22     RtlabApi.GetParameterControl(1)
23     RtlabApi.GetSignalControl(1)
24     RtlabApi.GetAcquisitionControl(1)
25
26     #Acquire signal
27     fileName='results'+str(test_num)
28     varName='Test_Auto'
29     RtlabApi.SetAcqWriteFile(0, fileName, varName, 1)
30
31     #Change the parameter
32     time.sleep(1)
33     paramValues = (paramPL)
34     RtlabApi.SetParametersByName(paramName, paramValues)
35     RtlabApi.SetSignalsByName(signalName, 1)
36     time.sleep(150) #Time for running a single test
37
38     #Release control
39     RtlabApi.SetAcqWriteFile(0, fileName, varName, 0)
40     RtlabApi.GetParameterControl(0)
41     RtlabApi.GetSignalControl(0)
42     RtlabApi.GetAcquisitionControl(0)
43     print('Model will be reset')
44
45     RtlabApi.Reset()
46     print('Model has been reset')
47
48 RtlabApi.OpenProject(projectName)
49 print('Project is open')
50
51 # Define Sequence Loop
52 MaxNumberOfSequence=10
53 test_num= range(1,MaxNumberOfSequence + 1)
54 paramPL = []
55 for _ in range(MaxNumberOfSequence):
56     random_value = round(random.uniform(0,1),2)
57     paramPL.append(random_value)
58 print paramPL
```

```
59 for j in test_num:
60     Test_Sequence(paramPL[j-1], j)
61 RtlabApi.CloseProject()
62 print('Model has been closed')
```

3.4.3 Outcome

As a part of the work undertaken in ERIGrid 2.0 towards improved and extended services (RI automation test), it can be established that this work has successfully:

- Defined the use cases and workflow for the automation testing approach,
- Demonstrated an automation PHIL test with the developed parameter sweeps script, and
- Created the communication that enables other RIs to participate in a geographically distributed automation test with the developed CM method in JRA2.3.

The list below shows the known limitations of the developed test automation approach:

- Identification of the controlled parameters' name and location for automated tests can be challenging for a complex system,
- The test execution time for each testing loop is not consistent as it will depend on the communication and hardware condition at the time of execution; this issue can vary the minimum value of running time per test,
- Some testing characteristics can only be changed and applied manually, which is not suitable for the automation approach; for example, in the above-demonstrated test, the test is intended to automatically change, the LVRT curves following country-specific grid codes which can only be modified manually.

4 Virtual Access

4.1 Simulation-as-a-Service Prototype

The main objective of the SaaS Prototype is to integrate existing simulation tools into a web-based platform for providing an offline simulation service which is hosted in the cloud and is easily accessible through a web browser. Therefore, this platform extends the usability of the Virtual Access (VA) infrastructures described in WP9-VA. Additionally, it can be integrated with Zenodo and other data service providers, to easily share relevant time series and power grid data. Based on this description, the following list of requirements was identified for the SaaS platform:

- Provides offline simulation, based on existing simulation tools, which are preferably open-source,
- Web-based, for improved accessibility, it is desirable to implement user-friendly interfaces, featuring well-known libraries for building scenarios and visualising simulation results,
- Hosted in the cloud, this will make it available to a broad audience and accessible through the Internet,
- Provides integration with standardised data models and communication protocols, enabling interoperability with the Data-as-a-Service (DaaS) platform, and
- Built with tools that facilitate its migration to cloud service providers which allows the platform to be easily adopted by other projects and contexts.

4.1.1 Platform Architecture

As part of the ERIGrid 2.0 project's consortium, Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen (RWTH) and the Automation of Complex Power Systems (ACS) institute have experience in building cloud-based solutions around topics related to the energy transition and digitalisation of energy. As part of its laboratory infrastructure, the ACS Institute has built its own private cloud, based on open tools such as *Kubernetes* and *OpenStack*. To fulfil the requirements of the SaaS platform listed above, the architecture shown in Figure 8 was proposed. The infrastructure layer is supported by the available Kubernetes cluster, where the main applications supporting the Simulation-as-a-Service platform are deployed. The different components shown in this architecture are described below.

JupyterHub

The key component of the application layer corresponds to Jupyterhub. This is a tool for managing access to Jupyter Notebooks. It allows multiple users to access these resources and execute them in an isolated environment. The simulator providing the SaaS functionality is integrated on top of JupyterHub.

DPSim

The open-source dynamic phasor simulator DPSim was chosen not only because it fulfils all of the requirements listed above, including direct integration with the JupyterHub application, but also because it has a reliable solver which has been validated against other well-known

Figure 8: Architecture of the SaaS prototype.

simulators (Mirz, Dinkelbach, & Monti, 2020). It does so using its Python interface, which exposes its objects and methods, which are implemented in C++, using the `pybind11` library. Moreover, DPsim has the following features:

- It supports both offline and real-time simulation.
- It allows to import scenarios that are defined through the Common Information Model (CIM) standard, which is a well-known standard for defining power systems, as well as scenarios from the Matpower¹ simulator.
- It supports online interaction using the VILLASnode² gateway. This allows co-simulation and Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) applications using a high variety of protocols such as User Datagram Protocol (UDP) sockets, Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) and Modbus. Furthermore, since VILLASnode constitutes one of the communication transports defined in WP12-JRA3 and supports the Universal Application Programming Interface (uAPI), it would be possible to build more complex co-simulation scenarios using the SaaS prototype.
- It includes an interface and an API allowing control of the execution of the simulation from an external application, thus extending its range of use cases

The high-level architecture of DPsim highlighting some of these features is shown in Figure 9 (Mirz, Vogel, Reinke, & Monti, 2019).

Pintura CIM Editor

Pintura is a web-based graphical reader and editor of power grids which uses the CIM standard as a data model. The graphical capabilities of Pintura are improved thanks to its integration

¹<https://matpower.org/>

²<https://www.fein-aachen.org/projects/villas-node/>

Figure 9: Architecture of the Dynamic Phasor Simulator, DPSim.

with the Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG) format. With this format, the schematic of the power network can be easily exported and then used in any kind of publication or report.

ownCloud

For data management, the proposed solution suggests to use of a local file management system providing functionalities to simplify the automation process for synchronisation through the use of APIs and scripts. A good alternative corresponds to ownCloud which is an open-source file management system that can be easily integrated into Kubernetes. Moreover, it features a powerful set of APIs for platform operations, file management operations and authentication. Thus, this setup allows the ownCloud's APIs and the Zenodo API to interact in both directions and keep the synchronisation and storage of relevant assets, mainly time series and grid models. The end user can populate this repository through direct interaction with Zenodo, making these assets available to the SaaS platform. On the other hand, the user can also store the simulation results or the built grid models into ownCloud that are automatically synchronised with Zenodo and made available to the stakeholders. In both cases, the use of appropriate Python libraries for interacting with the ownCloud API is required, which allows to fetch and publish the desired assets.

However, it needs to be clarified that, although it is also possible to integrate the Pintura editor with ownCloud, this functionality is not yet available.

4.1.2 Implementation and Results

The SaaS platform was implemented as part of the RWTH VA infrastructure and can be accessed in the ERIGrid 2.0³ web page. It contains the DPSim simulator alongside JupyterHub. The user is then able to build and run his own simulation scenarios or import them from CIM files using the corresponding functions provided by DPSim. Moreover, the platform includes

³<https://erigrd2.eu/vlab/>

a set of predefined tutorial-like Jupyter Notebooks which document and illustrate the use of DPSim. These Notebooks have been used successfully in a postgraduate course at RWTH to support the exercise sessions. Figure 10 shows a screenshot of one of these Jupyter Notebooks highlighting the voltages obtained from a power flow calculation.

Figure 10: Screenshot of one of the Jupyter notebooks of the SaaS prototype.

4.1.3 Open Issues and Future Work

Although the SaaS had a positive impact in the community, as evidenced in the Deliverable D6.3 (*D-NA5.2b Virtual Access Assessment Report, 2023*), there is currently an issue regarding its use for cryptomining tasks. Since any user can register to the ERIGrid 2.0 VA services, some accounts are being created by anonymous users to take advantage of the infrastructure and execute this malicious code. As a first attempt, the corresponding user accounts were blocked. However, in December of 2023, it was confirmed that this is not the long-term solution, as the process is not automated. For this reason, and by request of the RWTH information department, the SaaS was shut down until the problem was solved. The ERIGrid 2.0 consortium is currently working with the RWTH information department to solve this problem promptly.

5 Conclusions

To summarise, this report presented how the outcomes of WP12 have significantly advanced capabilities of RIs for integration, coupling, and automation. The three key implementations – a CM service, automation scripts for simulation configurations and runs, and the introduction of SaaS for virtual lab access – collectively represent a response to the evolving needs of RI environments.

The CM service enhances the automation and reproducibility of multi-RI experiments, ensuring consistency and reliability in research processes. Meanwhile, automation scripts streamline simulation tasks, thereby significantly improving efficiency. The deployment of SaaS for virtual lab access not only enhances accessibility but also promotes collaboration across diverse domains and RIs. These accomplishments represent a substantial step forward in bolstering the capabilities of RIs through innovative solutions. Future work will focus on implementing and incorporating the developed tools into workflows for joint multi-RI experiments.

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